

pH-metric Studies on the Mixed Ligand Chelates of Oxovanadium(IV) with Anthranilic Acid and Dicarboxylic or Hydroxy Acids

A. K. JAIN and G. K. CHATURVEDI

Chemical Laboratories, Agra College, Agra. (India)

Manuscript received 1 December 1978, revised 16 April 1979, accepted 4 August 1979

pH-metric study on the interaction of oxovanadium(IV) with anthranilic acid in presence of dicarboxylic—or hydroxy acids [where dicarboxylic acids=oxalic (OX), malonic (MALN), phthalic (PHA) and maleic (MAL) acids and hydroxy acids=salicylic (SA) and 5-sulfosalicylic (SSA) acids], indicates the formation of 1 : 1 : 1 chelates. The stability constants and free energies of formation (ΔF°) for the resulting bifunctional ligand chelates have been calculated at $35 \pm 1^\circ$ ($\mu=0.1M$ KNO₃).

THE binary complexes of the vanadyl ion with anthranilic acid¹, dicarboxylic acids² and hydroxy acids³ have been extensively studied. The ternary complexes of oxovanadium(IV) with dicarboxylic—or hydroxy acids have also been reported⁴⁻⁶. No work, however, appears to have been carried out on the ternary systems; VO²⁺-Anthranilic acid-Dicarboxylic-/Hydroxy acids (viz., OX, MALN, PHA, MAL, SA and SSA acids).

In the present communication the results on the potentiometric studies on these systems have been discussed.

Experimental

Materials :

All the chemicals used were either of A. R. (BDH) or G. R. (S. Merck) grade. A stock solution of vanadyl sulphate was prepared in doubly distilled water and standardised using standard method⁶. Solutions of anthranilic acid, OX, MALN, PHA, MAL, SA and SSA were prepared by direct weighing. Anthranilic acid was used as its monohydrochloride obtained by adding calculated volume of standard HCl to the calculated weighed amount of anthranilic acid. SSA was used as its monosodium salt. The concentration of all the ligand solutions were rechecked by pH titrations against 0.1 M KOH solution.

Method :

The following pH-metric titrations were performed—

- (1) 10 ml (0.025 M) ligand
- (2) 10 ml (0.025 M) ligand in presence of 10 ml (0.025 M) vanadyl sulphate (VO²⁺ : Ligand 1 : 1)

- (3) 10 ml (0.025 M) each of anthranilic acid hydrochloride and dicarboxylic-hydroxy acid in presence of 10 ml (0.025 M) vanadyl sulphate (VO²⁺ : Anthranilic acid : dicarboxylic-/hydroxy acid ; 1 : 1 : 1).

The pH titrations were carried out at $35 \pm 1^\circ$ (thermostatically maintained), with a precision Philips pH-meter (model PR 9405 M) with working accuracy ± 0.02 , using standard calomal (PV 9021) and glass (PV 9011) electrodes. The instrument was standardised against 0.05 M potassium hydrogen phthalate for pH=4, before use.

The ionic strength of all the solutions were kept constant ($\mu=0.1 M$ KNO₃) by adding 5 ml of 1 M KNO₃ to each solution and using low concentration of the ligand and the metal ion. The final volume was raised to 50 ml by mixing with a requisite volume of doubly distilled water at the beginning of each titration. All the titrations were performed in duplicate in order to establish the reproducibility of the measurements.

Calculations :

The acid dissociation constants of the dicarboxylic and hydroxy acids were calculated by Chaberek and Martell⁷ and the stability constants ($\log K_{MLL'}$) of the ternary species by the method of Ramamoorthy and Santappa⁸, according to which—

$$K_{MLL'} = \frac{T_M - 1/2(A)(X)}{(1/2)^2(A)^2(X)} (T_M = T_L = T_{L'})$$

where,

$$A = \frac{4T_M - T_{OH} - H^+}{2H^+ + \frac{4(H^+)^2}{K_2 + K_2'} + \frac{4(H^+)^3}{(K_1 K_2) + (K_1' K_2')}}}$$

and

$$X = 1 + \frac{2H^+}{K_2 + K_2'} + \frac{2(H^+)^2}{(K_1 K_2) + (K_1' K_2')}$$

T_M = Total (VO^{2+}) , T_L = Total (L) , $T_{L'}$ = Total (L') ;

A = Total free ligand concentration ;

H = free hydrogen ion concentration.

$K_1 K_2, K_1' K_2'$ are the first and second dissociation constants of the ligands L and L' respectively.

The pK values of the ligands are presented in Table 1. The values of stability constants (log

TABLE 1—ACID DISSOCIATION CONSTANT OF THE LIGANDS AT $35 \pm 1^\circ$

Ligands	pK_1	pK_2
Anthranilic acid hydrochloride	1.93 ± 0.23	$4.75 \pm 0.05(4.89)$
OX	$1.54 \pm 0.19(1.24)$	$4.10 \pm 0.06(4.10)$
MALN	$2.73 \pm 0.10(2.75)$	$5.34 \pm 0.09(5.36)$
PHA	$3.16 \pm 0.08(3.10)$	$5.40 \pm 0.12(5.29)$
MAL	$1.98 \pm 0.16(1.92)$	$6.36 \pm 0.04(6.22)$
SA	$3.01 \pm 0.08(2.97)$	13.60^{11}
SSA	$2.70 \pm 0.06(2.68)$	$11.40 \pm 0.04(11.42)$

Values given in brackets are taken from literature.

TABLE 2a—STABILITY CONSTANTS (log $K_{MLL'}$) AND FREE ENERGIES OF FORMATION (ΔF°) AT $35 \pm 1^\circ$

m	$T_M \times 10^{-3}$	$T_{OH} \times 10^{-3}$	VO ²⁺ —Anthranilic-OX		VO ²⁺ —Anthranilic-MALN	
			pH	log $K_{MLL'}$	pH	log $K_{MLL'}$
0.1	4.975	0.497	1.98	9.49	2.06	10.84
0.2	4.970	0.990	2.00	9.47	2.08	10.78
0.3	4.926	1.477	2.02	9.44	2.10	10.75
0.4	4.902	1.96	2.04	9.39	2.12	10.72
0.5	4.878	2.43	2.06	9.37	2.14	10.69
0.6	4.854	2.91	2.08	9.35	2.16	10.65
0.7	4.831	3.38	2.10	9.33	2.18	10.66
0.8	4.807	3.84	2.12	9.32	2.20	10.61
0.9	4.784	4.30	2.14	9.26	2.22	10.60
1.0	4.761	4.76	2.16	9.33	2.24	10.58
1.1	4.739	5.21	2.18	9.29	2.26	10.60
1.2	4.716	5.66	2.20	9.29	2.28	10.59
1.3	4.694	6.10	2.23	9.23	2.31	10.56
1.4	4.672	6.54	2.26	9.18	2.34	10.45
1.5	4.651	6.97	2.29	9.13	2.37	10.40
1.6	4.629	7.40	2.32	9.10	2.40	10.37*
1.7	4.608	7.88	2.35	9.06*	2.43	10.34*
1.8	4.587	8.23	2.39	8.98*	2.46	10.31*

Mean values
 ΔF° (K cal/mole)

9.29 ± 0.19
-13.08

10.62 ± 0.22
-14.96

m = moles of base added per mole of the metal ion or ligand ;

T_M = total metal ion concentration ;

T_{OH} = total alkali used.

* Values omitted.

TABLE 2b—STABILITY CONSTANTS (log $K_{MLL'}$) AND FREE ENERGIES OF FORMATION (ΔF°) AT $35 \pm 1^\circ$

m	VO ²⁺ —Anthranilic-PHA		VO ²⁺ —Anthranilic-MAL		VO ²⁺ —Anthranilic-SA		VO ²⁺ —Anthranilic-SSA	
	pH	log $K_{MLL'}$	pH	log $K_{MLL'}$	pH	log $K_{MLL'}$	pH	log $K_{MLL'}$
0.1	2.17	9.58	2.10	10.50	2.04	11.06*	2.12	10.40*
0.2	2.20	9.58	2.12	10.47	2.06	11.00*	2.14	10.29*
0.3	2.23	9.54	2.14	10.44	2.09	10.84	2.17	10.25*
0.4	2.26	9.50	2.16	10.51	2.12	10.77	2.20	10.05
0.5	2.29	9.45	2.18	10.40	2.15	10.67	2.23	10.01
0.6	2.32	9.38	2.21	10.28	2.18	10.57	2.26	9.91
0.7	2.35	9.31	2.24	10.24	2.21	10.48	2.29	9.86
0.8	2.38	9.29	2.27	10.16	2.24	10.40	2.32	9.80
0.9	2.41	9.25	2.30	10.09	2.27	10.31*	2.35	9.73
1.0	2.44	9.22	2.33	10.02	2.30	10.24*	2.38	9.70
1.1	2.48	9.22	2.36	9.98	2.34	10.17*	2.42	9.61
1.2	2.52	9.10*	2.40	9.87*	—	—	2.46	9.50*
1.3	2.56	9.01*	2.44	9.77*	—	—	2.50	9.40*

Mean values
 ΔF° (K cal/mole)

10.24 ± 0.26
-14.42

10.62 ± 0.22
-14.96

9.83 ± 0.22
-13.85

* Values omitted.

Note : Values of T_M and T_{OH} corresponding to the values of m given in the Table 2a remain unaltered and hence they have been omitted in Table 2b.

K_{ML}) and free energies of formation (ΔF°) are recorded in Tables 2a and 2b.

The stability constants for the resulting hetero-ligand ternary complexes were determined in the lower pH buffer region, as it is well known that in lower pH range (1.5 to 3.5) the hydrolysis of VO^{2+} ion may be completely neglected⁹.

Results and Discussion

The curves for the systems : VO^{2+} - Anthranilic acid - OX/SA, are exhibited in the Figs. 1 and 2 respectively as representative (for the systems involving dicarboxylic-/hydroxy acids). The curves for the other systems have been omitted for the sake of brevity.

Curve a, Figs. 1 and 2, showing the potentiometric titration of anthranilic acid monohydrochloride with KOH, exhibit inflection at $m=1$ and at $m=2$ (m being the moles of base added per mole of the metal ion or ligand), indicating that the ligand acts as a dibasic acid.

Curve b, Figs. 1 and 2, representing the potentiometric titration of vanadyl sulphate with KOH in the presence of an equimolar amount of anthranilic acid hydrochloride, exhibits an inflection at $m=4$, probably, attributed to the formation of 1 : 1 complex and its hydrolysis¹.

Similarly the curve d/d', Figs. 1 and 2, representing the titration of vanadyl sulphate in the presence of an equimolar amount of dicarboxylic acid (OX, MALN, PHA, MAL) and hydroxy acids (SA and K - SSA), may be interpreted in terms of

the formation of 1 : 1 binary complexes and their hydrolysis^{2,3,5}.

Mixed Ligand Chelates :

The curve e/e', Figs. 1 and 2, represent the 1 : 1 : 1, VO^{2+} - Anthranilic acid - OX/SA systems respectively.

A weak inflection at about $m=4$ in the titration curve e/e' for the mixed ligand systems discussed above, may be attributed to the complete neutralization of protons of anthranilic acid monohydrochloride and dicarboxylic or hydroxy acid, made labile as a result of chelation. Considering VO^{2+} - Anthranilic acid - OX/SA as representative, the overall reaction may be represented as :

The formation of heteroligand ternary species in these systems is further evidenced by ;

- (i) lowering in pH in comparison with the binary systems.
- (ii) Non-appearance of solid phase and significant colour changes observed during the titration.
- (iii) Non-superimposable nature of the theoretical composite curves (drawn by adding horizontal distances of the curves representing the binary systems and free ligands)¹⁰.

The data given in Table 2 indicate the following order of stability of ternary complexes in terms of dicarboxylic or hydroxy acids :

- (i) MALN > OX
- (ii) MAL > PHA
- (iii) SA > SSA

The relative stabilities of the mixed ligand chelates involving MALN and OX, MAL and PHA follow the order of the basicities of these ligands. In the case of complexes of SA and SSA, the relative order may be explained on the basis of the presence of sulphonic group in SSA and the steric factors as reported by Tandon et al^{1,2}. The sulphonate group increases the acidity of the phenolic group and thus probably, results in the formation of less stable complex. The steric factor increases with increasing size of the ligand and, therefore, decreases the stability of the resulting chelate. In the case of SA and SSA the relative stability may also be attributed to the basicities of these ligands.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their gratitude to Prof. J. P. Tandon, Head of Chemistry Department, Rajasthan University, Jaipur, Dr. R. C. Sharma and Dr. (Km.) Vinod, Chemistry Department, Agra College, Agra for their valuable suggestions during these investigations. Thanks are also due to Dr. S. M. L. Gupta, Head of Chemistry Department, Agra College, Agra for providing laboratory facilities and to the CSIR for providing financial assistance (JRF) to one of the authors (AKJ).

References

1. S. P. SINGH and J. P. TANDON, *Monatshefte fur Chemie*, 1975, **106**, 871.
2. S. P. SINGH and J. P. TANDON, *Acta Chim. Acad. Scientiarum Hungaricae*, Tomus 1974, **80**(4), 425.
3. S. P. SINGH and J. P. TANDON, *Bulletin De L' Academie, Polonaise Des Sciences*, 1974, Vol. 22, No. 8.
4. S. P. SINGH and J. P. TANDON, *Monatshefte fur Chemie*, 1975, **106**, 271.
5. A. K. JAIN, R. C. SHARMA and G. K. CHATURVEDI, *Polish Journal of Chemistry (Formerly Roczniki Chemii)*, 1978, **52**, 259.
6. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis" 2nd Edn., **III**, 94, pp. 319.
7. S. CHABEREK and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 5052.
8. S. RAMAMOORTHY and M. SANTAPPA, *Indian Journal of Chemistry*, 1971, **9**(4), 381.
9. M. BARTUSEK, L. SOMMER, F. J. C. ROSSOTTI and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, Leipzig, 1964, **226**, 309; *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1955, **9**, 1177.
10. G. H. OARBY and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 2859.
11. L. G. SILLEN and A. E. MARTELL, "Stability Constants", 2nd Edn. London, The Chemical Society (1964).